

AL- FALAH INTERNATIONAL TOURS & TRAVELS, HAJJ & UMRAH

2nd floor, Meepiri Centre, Kumbala. Ph: 04998-217277 Mob: 9895064777, 9744647786
E-mail: alfalah.intl77@gmail.com, www.alfalahintl.com

Ref.

Date 22/04/2022.....

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr.SAHAD M.A[2SU19HN029],STUDENT OF INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT &COMMERCE SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY,CITY CAMPUS PANDESHWARA, MANGALORE, has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of sales and marketing from 29/01/2022 to 21/04/2022 under the guidance of Mr.SUBAIR SA(MANAGER),

During the period of his internship program with us he had been exposed to different process was found punctual, hardworking and inquisitive.

We wish him every success in his life and career.

For AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL

Company Certificate

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

B.c Road Bantwal Taluk
Dakshina Kannada

REF NO: UBI21-22-1

DATE: 23-06-2022

CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to Certify that Mr. **VIJESH.V.POOJARY** (Reg No: **2SU19HN039**), final year BBA student of Institute of Management And Commerce **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** has done his project work "**A STUDY ON CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT WITH THE REFERENCE TO UNION BANK IS INDIA, BCROAD**" during the period of three months from **JANUARY 1st 2021 to 31th MARCH 2022** under the guidance of **Mr. JAGDISH PRASAD**, manager, **UNION BANK OF INDIA, BCROAD.**

"We wish him/her all the success in her/hid future endeavours"

कृते यूनियन बँक ऑफ इंडिया
For UNION BANK OF INDIA

P. Jagdish
प्रबंधक Manager

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

Darul basra aijanadka, K.C Road, kotekar, Mangalore -22

DATE: 30-03-2022

CRETIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. MOHAMMED SHIAHAN (Reg no. 2SU19HN023), final year BBA student of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE has successfully completed his internship project titled "A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS OXYEBLUE ,MANGALORE" during the period Jan 1st 2022 to March 30th 2022 at our organization- OXYEBLUE ,MANGALORE .

We found him to be sincere and hardworking during the course of internship with us

"We wish him all the success in his future endeavors"

[Managing partner]

Candidate signature

Experience cum Relieving Certificate

To,
Fahad Baba Sayyad
Bangalore

This is to certify that **Fahad Baba Sayyad**, employed with **Zolostays Property Solutions Pvt. Ltd.** has been relieved from the services of the company at the close of the working hours on **24 April 2022**. Here are the details of the employment:

Name of the Department	College Demand
Employee Code	ZSIN00470
Last Designation Held	Intern
Date of Joining	13 January 2022
Date of Leaving	24 April 2022

In case of any queries, please feel free to reach out to hr@zolostays.com

Yours faithfully,
For **Zolostays Property Solutions Pvt. Ltd.**

Ramesh Nair
Associate Director - Human Resources
Date: 24 April 2022
Place: Bangalore

ZOLOSTAYS PROPERTY SOLUTIONS PRIVATE LIMITED

Registered Address
No. 1100, 22nd Cross, HSR Layout,
Sector 3, Bangalore, KA-560102, India

Ph: 86 8010 8010
www.zolostays.com
CIN U74900KA2015PT C080643

CERTIFICATE OF TRAINING

Date: 16-04-2022

This Certificate is proudly presented to Mr. Yasar Arhab for successfully completing
The work experience program in our sales department from 13th January 2022 to 12th
April 2022 at our Mussafah office Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates.

We wish you all the very best for your future endeavors

Sincerely,

Abdullah

HR Manager

COLLEGE CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Miss. AISHWARYA HB. is a bonafide student of BBA-IB final semester (2020-2021batch) at SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, college of commerce and management, Pandeshwar City campus, Mangalore. This project report titled "INTERNSHIP REPORT". Has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of BACHELOR OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION-INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS under the supervision of DR. ROBIN SHINDE, Srinivas University.

DATE: 26.08.2021

PLACE: MANGALORE

Prof. KEERTHANA RAJ

DEAN

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Transform yourself

INTERNSHIP EXPERIENCE CERTIFICATE

To, FATHIMA RISWANA C P,

This is to certify that **MS.FATHIMA RISWANA C P,D/O ARIF C. P,** has successfully completed her Internship from 15th March 2021 - 30th June 2021. During Internship tenure we found her extremely resourceful in all the tasks that were given.

The project undertaken by her was in HR, vertical as an Intern for Inmovidu Tech.

We found her to be a good team player besides being a hard worker. I hereby certify her work was satisfactory to the best of my knowledge.

We wish her success in her future endeavors.

Yours truly,

Ms. Anusha

HR Manager

InMovidu Technologies Private Limit

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. MOHAMMED THAMEEM, student of Srinivas university of management and commerce has successfully completed his Internship project titled travel and marketing from 5 January to 3 March in our organization – AR TRAVELS

We found him to be sincere and hardworking during the course of his internship with us

We wish him all the best in his future endeavors"

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

ELITE EDUWISE

One wise association for many great careers

Reg: AAY-8166

INTERNSHIP CERTIFICATE

To Whom It May Concern:

This is to certify that Afiya Banu was working at Elite Eduwise as "Digital Marketing and sales intern" from 01/01/2022 to 30/03/2022.

During this period, her services were found to be satisfactory in carrying out the job duties.

Work Responsibilities - were to:

- Participate/ Conduct workshops, committees, and conferences designed to promote intellectual, social, and physical welfare of students.
- Prepare digital marketing content and promote social media pages.
- Counsel and guide students to choose the right courses for higher studies.
- Career guidance.
- Writing and proofreading creative copies.
- Respond to case related queries.
- Handling sales calls.
- Monitoring performances.
- Coordinating internal marketing and organizations culture

We wish her all the best in her future.

Suhan Kabeer

CEO, Managing Partner

Elite Eduwise

Bangalore - 34

2/3, 2nd Floor, Sony World Junction,
Koramangala, Bangalore - 560034

9149599978 / 7411381302

info@eliteeduwisecom

29th June 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

INTERNSHIP CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. TILAK R (Reg. No.2SU19HN038)** student at SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY Pandeshwara, Mangalore-575001 has successfully completed his internship at Prestige Mangalore Retail Ventures Pvt. Ltd. from 28th January 2022 – 28th April 2022 (3 Months) and submitted project report for the same.

We found him sincere & hardworking while undergoing project work.

We wish him best of luck in his future endeavors.

Yours sincerely
For and on behalf of Prestige Mangalore Retail Ventures Private Limited.

Arvind Shrivastav
Centre Head

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

 आर.सी. 1st Maharashtra		
	ई-मेल/e-mail : bom381@mahabank.co.in प्रधान कार्यालय लोकमंगल 1501 शिवाजीनगर, पुणे-5 Head Office LOKMANGAL 1501 SHIVAJINAGAR PUNE-5	

Ref No	AG16/Project/Shreyas/2022-23	Date	17.06.2022
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CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to Certify that Mr. SHREYAS S SALIYAN (Reg No: 2SU19HN035), final year BBA student of Institute of Management And Commerce SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY has done his project work "A STUDY ON FINANCIAL SERVICES OFFERED BY THE BANK WITH THE REFERENCE TO BANK OF MAHARASHTRA, MANGALORE" during the period of three months from 31st DECEMBER 2021 to 31st MARCH 2022 under the guidance of Mr. SUCHETH M D'SOUZA, Chief Manager, BANK OF MAHARASHTRA, MANGALORE BRANCH.

"We wish him all the success in his future endeavours"

For

Bank of Maharashtra
बँक ऑफ महाराष्ट्र
For Bank of Maharashtra

for:
Chief Manager / मंगलूर
Branch Manager / Mangalore
Mangalore Branch

ZAIN MOTORS

Authorised Dealer for Bajaj Auto Limited

GSTIN : 32AJJPM1117A1Z0

Date : 10-05-2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. ABDUL REHMAN ZIYAD S/o Mr. KHALID** as a student of **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE, CITY CAMPUS, PANDESHWAR, MANGALORE** for the award of **BACHELOR DEGREE IN BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION (B.B.A)** having **REG. NO. 2SU19HN002** has undergone his Internship in our organization as a part of his project.

During his tenure of three month from 19-01-2022 to 18-04-2022 , we found **Mr. ABDUL REHMAN ZIYAD** to be Hard Working, Conscientious, Dedicated and responsible in study and we wish his all the best in future.

For ZAIN MOTORS

[Handwritten Signature]
General Manager

General Manager

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. MOHAMMED THAMEEM ,student of Srinivas university of management and commerce has successfully completed his internship project titled travel and marketing from 5january to 30march in our organization – AR TRAVELS

We found him to be sincere and hardworking during the course of his internship with us

"We wish him all the best in his future endeavors"

For AR TRAVELS

REF: MANG/HRD/3593/2022-23

DATE: 24/05/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. SATHWIK SHETTY**, student of Bachelor of Business Administration, 2SU19HN030, Srinivasa College of Management and Commerce, Mangalore. He completed his Internship towards the partial fulfillment of the requirements for the course of Bachelor Of Business Administration [BBA] in our organization.

He has worked as an Intern from **01st January 2022 to 31st March 2022** and submitted study report with reference to **Advertisement Management with reference to Mandovi Motors Private Limited, Mangalore.**

This certificate is issued on request of the student as support document to be furnish along with project report.

We wish him good luck.

For Mandovi Motors Private Limited.,

For MANDOVIMOTORS PRIVATE LIMITED
RAJESH BHAT M
A.M. - HUMAN RESOURCES
HR Manager

Company certificate

MANGALORE
ASSOCIATES

02.06.2022

Ref.

Date

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Mohammed Rihaan (Reg No: 2SU19HN021), student of BBA (HONOURS), Srinivas University, Mangalore, has successfully completed his internship at Mangalore Associates, Mangalore during the period from 15.01.2022 to 15.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working. We wish him all the best in his future endeavour.

AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL TOURS & TRAVELS, HAJJ & UMRAH

2nd floor, Meepiri Centre, Kumbala. Ph: 04998-217277 Mob: 9895064777, 9744647788
E-mail: alfalah.intl77@gmail.com, www.alfalahintl.com

Ref.

Date:

22/04/2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr GURUPRASAD AN [2SU19HN014]**, STUDENT OF INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, CITY CAMPUS PANDESHWARA, MANGALORE, has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of Finance from 29/01/2022 to 21/04/2022 under the guidance of **Mr SUBAIR SA (MANAGER)**.

During the period of his internship program with us he had been exposed to different process was found punctual, hardworking and inquisitive.

We wish him every success in his life and career.

For **AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL**

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

KAN/RZ/S8212/06/2022/21

Date: 09/06/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Rohit Ram Karkera Reg. No. 2SU19HN028 pursuing Bachelors in Business Administration (BBA) from Srinivas University Mangalore. Has successfully completed his Internship in Customer Satisfaction from CR Department from M/s. Kanchana Automobiles Private Limited, Mangalore. (Dealer for Hyundai Motors India Limited dealing with Hyundai Passenger Cars) from 06-01-2022 to 05-04-2022.

During his training, we found him to be sincere, dedicated, committed and hardworking.

Team Kanchana wishes him good luck and all the very best for his future endeavor.

For Kanchana Automobiles Pvt Ltd
FOR HEAD HR

24/06/22
KANCHANA AUTOMOBILES PVT LTD
[HR & Admin]

Company certificate

Darul Beera ajjenodha, K.C Road, betohar, Mangalore -22

DATE: 30-09-2022

CRETIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. ABDUL KHADER AMAN (REG no. 25U19HN001), final year BBA student of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE has successfully completed his Internship project titled "A STUDY ON BRAND AWARENESS & CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS OXYEBLUE" during the period Jan 1st 2022 to March 30th 2022 at our organization-OXYEBLUE, MANGALORE.

We found him to be sincere and hardworking during the course of internship with us
"We wish him all the success in his future endeavors"

[Managing partner].

Candidate signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'AK' with a flourish.

Company certificate

Derul beara aJanadka, R.C Road, hotohar, Mangalore -22

DATE: 30-03-2022

CRETIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. ABDUL KHADER AMAN (REG no. 2SU19HN001)**, final year BBA student of **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE** has successfully completed his Internship project titled **"A STUDY ON BRAND AWARENESS & CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS OXYEBLUE"** during the period Jan 1st 2022 to March 30th 2022 at our organization-**OXYEBLUE, MANGALORE**.

We found him to be sincere and hardworking during the course of internship with us
"We wish him all the success in his future endeavors"

[Managing partner].

Candidate signature

KASTURBA HOSPITAL MANIPAL

(An associate Hospital of MAHE, Manipal)

30th April 2022

TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to confirm that, **Mr. Shahim V P** (Reg No-2SU19HA003), BBA student, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru has undergone an Internship training at various departments of Operations under the guidance of Mr. Jibu Thomas, Chief Manager-Operations, Kasturba Hospital, Manipal during the month of February to April 2022.

During this period, we found Mr. Shahim P to be dedicated and committed towards his training and we wish him all the success in his future endeavors.

* Medical Superintendent

Post Box No. 7, Manipal-576104, Karnataka, India. Phone : +91 - 820 - 2571201 - 2571210 (10 lines)
Fax : +91 - 820 - 2571934. Email : office.kh@manipal.edu

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

 MARUTI SUZUKI ARENA

REF: MANG/HRD/3594/2022-23

DATE: 24/05/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. SAHIL M RAI**, student of Bachelor of Business Administration, 2SU19HIN030, Srinivasa College of Management and Commerce, Mangalore. He completed his Internship towards the partial fulfillment of the requirements for the course of Bachelor Of Business Administration [BBA] in our organization.

He has worked as an Intern from **01st January 2022 to 31st March 2022** and submitted study report with reference to **Salesmanship with reference to Mandovi Motors Private Limited, Mangalore.**

This certificate is issued on request of the student as support document to be furnish along with project report.

We wish him good luck.

For Mandovi Motors Private Limited.,

For MANDOVIMOTORS PRIVATE LIMITED

RAJESH BHAT M

A.M. HUMAN RESOURCES

Arvind Building, Dr. Shivarama Karantha Road, Hampankatta, Mangaluru - 575001.
Ph.:Sales: 0824-2410128, Mob.: 9980180128 | Website: www.mandovimotors.in | Email: agmsales@mandovi.net
GST NO: 29AACCM4309H123 PAN: AACCM4309H CBN: U34300KA1999PTC024799

**MANDOVI MOTORS
PRIVATE LIMITED**

Company certificate

MANGALORE
ASSOCIATES

Ref.

02.06.2022

Date

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Mohammed Rihaan (Reg No: 2SU19HN021), student of BBA (HONOURS), Srinivas University, Mangalore, has successfully completed his internship at Mangalore Associates, Mangalore during the period from 15.01.2022 to 15.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working. We wish him all the best in his future endeavour.

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL TOURS & TRAVELS, HAJJ & UMRAH

2nd floor, Meepiri Centre, Kumbala. Ph: 04998-217277 Mob: 9895064777, 9744647786
E-mail: alfalah.intl77@gmail.com, www.alfalahintl.com

Ref.

Date:

22/04/2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr.ABDUL SAHAD[2SU19HN003],STUDENT OF INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT &COMMERCE SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY,CITY CAMPUS PANDESHWARA, MANGALORE**, has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of sales and marketing from 29/01/2022 to 21/04/2022 under the guidance of **Mr.SUBAIR SA(MANAGER)**,

During the period of his internship program with us he had been exposed to different process was found punctual, hardworking and inquisitive.

We wish him every success in his life and career.

For **AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL**

Partner

KANACHUR
INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES

DERALAKATTE
MANGALURU - 575 018
Phone : 0824 - 2888999
E-mail : hr@kanachur.edu.in

14.06.2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to Certify that Mr. Thejus Bobby Philip, Reg. No. 2SU19HN037 student of Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed his internship in our Kanachur Hospital & Research Centre, Natekal, Mangalore on the topic "Work Life Balance of Employees at Kanachur Hospital & Research Centre" for a period from 06.01.2022 to 06.04.2022.

During this period his conduct and performance were found good. We wish him all the best for his future endeavors.

14/06/22

HR Manager

29th June 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

INTERNSHIP CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. TILAK R (Reg. No.2SU19HN038)** student at SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY Pandeshwara, Mangalore-575001 has successfully completed his internship at Prestige Mangalore Retail Ventures Pvt. Ltd. from 28th January 2022 – 28th April 2022 (3 Months) and submitted project report for the same.

We found him sincere & hardworking while undergoing project work.

We wish him best of luck in his future endeavors.

Yours sincerely
For and on behalf of Prestige Mangalore Retail Ventures Private Limited.

Arvind Shrivastav
Centre Head

Company Certificate

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

B.c Road Bantwal Taluk
Dakshina Kannada

REF NO: UBI21-22-1

DATE: 23-06-2022

CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to Certify that Mr. **VIJESH.V.POOJARY** (Reg No: **2SU19HN039**), final year BBA student of Institute of Management And Commerce **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** has done his project work "**A STUDY ON CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT WITH THE REFERENCE TO UNION BANK IS INDIA, BCROAD**" during the period of three months from **JANUARY 1st 2021** to **31th MARCH 2022** under the guidance of **Mr. JAGDISH PRASAD**, manager, **UNION BANK OF INDIA, BCROAD.**

"We wish him/her all the success in her/hid future endeavours"

कृते यूनियन बैंक ऑफ इंडिया
For UNION BANK OF INDIA

P. Jagdish
प्रबंधक Manager

KERALA STATE RUBBER CO-OPERATIVE LTD

RUBCO HOUSE SOUTHBAZAR, KANNUR 670 002 KERALA INDIA

Ph:91 4972709749,2711134,2711378,91-4972711030

Website: www.rubcogroup.com, Email: info@rubcomail.com

Date: 23rd may2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. AKSHAY (Reg No. 2SU19IB001), BBA student of institute of management and commerce, city campus Pandeshwar, Mangalore. Srinivas University has successfully completed his project titled "A STUDY ON HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT WITH REFERENCE TO KERALA STATE RUBBER CO-OPERATIVE LTD, KANNUR. In our organisation for a period of 3 months commencing from 21/01/2022-20/04/2022 he has completed the project satisfactorily.

We wish All the best in his careers.

For Kerala State Rubber Co-operative Ltd.,

General Manager (HR) etc.

30/04/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms.Chaitra (Reg No:2SU19IB002), Final Year Student of BBA International Business from Srinivas University College Of Management And Commerce Mangalore, has Successfully Completed her Internship Under HR Activities at MAX HYPERMARKET INDIA PVT.LTD. (SPAR_Forum Mall) MANGALORE from 15/01/2022 to 30/04/2022.

We found her sincere, hardworking, and technically sound and result oriented. She worked well as part of a team during her tenure.

We wish her All the Best in her future endeavors.

For Max Hypermarket India Pvt. Ltd.

Snigdha Raj
Ex.Business HR

 LANDMARK
GROUP

MAX HYPERMARKET INDIA PVT.
GF 29&30, No 19-B-484/09
Forum Mall, Magaladevi Temple Road
Attavar Village, Cantonment Ward
Pandalayur,
Mangalore-575001
PHONE: +0824-2498122
WEBSITE: www.sparindia.com
CIN: L52180KA2004PT003788

K. SHRINATH HEBBAR
Proprietor

MILESTONE2S

5th Floor, Shop No.514,
Door No. 15-5-223/140,
Collectors Gate Junction,
Balmatta, Mangalore - 575002.
E-Mail: info@landtrades.in

2nd May 2022

To Whomsoever It May Concern

Sub: Internship program at Land Trades Builders & Developers.

This is to certify that Ms. Hridima M V (Reg. No. 2SU19IB003), student of Final Year B.B.A. (International Business) at College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, has completed her Internship at Land Trades Builders & Developers for the period commencing from the 1st January 2022 upto the 30th April 2022 in order to acquire the necessary understanding of business operations.

During the course of her Internship, she has been found to be sincere in executing her tasks.

We wish her all the best in her endeavours.

Thanking You.

Yours Sincerely,

For Land Trades Builders & Developers

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be "H. S. B.", is written over the typed name of the Chief Executive Officer.

(Chief Executive Officer)

**GROUP OF ANOTHER SIDE OF
HUMAN RESOURCE
CAREER TRAINING AND JOB PLACEMENT**

Date: 10/05/2022

This is certifying that Mr. Ikshitha has worked with as a Human Resource Assistant from 1st of January 2022 till 19th of April 2022 and Successfully Completed her Internship of 75days

In this period, she has shown full Sincerity, Dedication and Hard work towards her concerned job, which has helped in improving the management of the company.

This is to inform that Ikshitha has been relieved from all other duties. I wish her good luck and great future ahead.

Thanking you

**For GROUP OF ANOTHER SIDE OF
HUMAN RESOURCE**

Group of Another side of human Resource

Kerala State Cashew Workers Apex
Industrial Co-operative Society Ltd.

P. B. No. 262, Industrial Development Plot
H & C Compound, Mundakkal West, Kollam 691 001

Reg No. IND (ST) 12

Phone : 0474 - 2742499, 2765644

FAX - 0474-2747153

email : cashewcapex@rediffmail.com

website : www.cashewcapex.com

15.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr.Litto Boban, {Reg.No.2SU19IB005} B.B.A {International Bussiness} student of Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka has completed "AN INTERNSHIP PROGRAMME AT CAPEX" from 12.01.2022 to 31.03.2022. He has completed the Internship programme satisfactorily. During his association with us, he was very keen and enthusiastic in his work.

We wish him all the best in future endeavors.

Managing Director

KONKAN SPECIALITY POLYPRODUCTS PRIVATE LIMITED

Plot No. 37, KIADB Industrial Area, Baikampady, Mangalore-
575 011 Phone: +91-824-2408129 / 2409274 Fax: +91-824-2408657

E-mail: info@konspec.com Website: www.konspec.com

Ref: KSPPL/HR/30/2022-23

Date: 30.04.2022

Certificate

This is to certify that Mr. Sachin Kumar Poonia (Reg No: 2SU19IB007), BBA-IB student of Srinivas University, Mangalore has completed Internship programme from 15th January 2022 to 30th April 2022, as a partial fulfillment of degree in BBA-IB Programme.

During this period we found him sincere, hardworking and he bears a good moral conduct. We wish him all the very best for his future endeavors.

For **KONKAN SPECIALITY POLYPRODUCTS PVT.LTD.**

SANTHOSH K

ASSISTANT MANAGER- HR & ADMIN

To

Mr. Abhiram S Potham
Narayana Nivas
Perlassery
Mundalur PO
Kannur – 670622

INTERNSHIP EXPERIENCE CERTIFICATE

Dear Mr. Abhiram,

This is to certify that Mr. Abhiram S Pothan has successfully completed his internship from 29th March 2021 to 30th June 2021 (3 Months). During his internship tenure we found him extremely resourceful in all the task that were given

The project undertaken by him was "SALES PROMOTION" on sales with **PIONEER CARS (INDIA) PRIVATE LIMITED (PEEYEM HYUNDAI)**

We found him to be a good team player besides being a hard worker. I hereby certify that his work was absolutely satisfactory to the best of my knowledge

We wish him all success in his future endeavors.

For Pioneer Cars (India) Private Ltd,

Deputy Manager - HR

INTERNSHIP CERTIFICATE

To,
Whomsoever it may concern.

This is to certify that MUHAMMED FATHEEN BIN FASIL has done his internship in the sales team at KIRA KIRA BRANDS, Bangalore, from 16.04.2021 to 16.07.2021.

He has worked on a project titled JusBrick. This project was aimed at making sales calls and converting as many leads as possible. As part of the project, he has managed to onboard more than the anticipated number clients in the span of three months.

During his internship he has demonstrated his skills with self-motivation to learn new skills. His performance exceeded our expectations and he was able to onboard many clients in a short time.

We wish him all the best for his upcoming career.

Sincerely,

**NAMRATA KUMAR,
CEO**

To
Ms. Farsana KP
Kammanaparamba House
Velliparanba PO
Calicut 673008

INTERNSHIP EXPERIENCE CERTIFICATE

Dear Ms. Farsana KP

This is to certify that Ms. Farsana KP has successfully completed her internship from 29th March 2021 to 30th June 2021 (3 Months). During her internship tenure we found her extremely resourceful in all the task that were given

The project undertaken by her was "SALES PROMOTION" on sales with **PIONEER CARS (INDIA) PRIVATE LIMITED (PEEYEM HYUNDAI)**

We found her to be a good team player besides being a hard worker. I hereby certify that her work was absolutely satisfactory to the best of my knowledge

We wish her all success in his future endeavors.

For Pioneer Cars (India) Private Ltd,

Deputy Manager - HR

Experience cum Relieving Certificate

To,
Shriram Anutej K
Bangalore

This is to certify that **Shriram Anutej K**, employed with **Zolostays Property Solutions Pvt. Ltd.** has been relieved from the services of the company at the close of the working hours on **7 May 2022**. Here are the details of the employment:

Name of the Department	College Demand
Employee Code	ZSIN00472
Last Designation Held	Intern
Date of Joining	24 January 2022
Date of Leaving	7 May 2022

In case of any queries, please feel free to reach out to hr@zolostays.com

Yours faithfully,
For **Zolostays Property Solutions Pvt. Ltd.**

Ramesh Nair
Associate Director - Human Resources
Date: 7 May 2022
Place: Bangalore

ZOLOSTAYS PROPERTY SOLUTIONS PRIVATE LIMITED

Ph: 88 8010 8010
www.zolostays.com
CIN U74900KA2015PTC080643

Registered Address
No. 1190, 22nd Cross, HSR Layout,
Sector 3, Bangalore, KA-560102, India

Transform yourself

INTERNSHIP EXPERIENCE CERTIFICATE

To Omkar Nagesh Punage,

This is to certify that **Mr. Omkar Nagesh Punage** has successfully completed his Internship from 20th March 2021 - 20th June 2021. During Internship tenure we found him extremely resourceful in all the tasks that were given.

The project undertaken by him was in “Business Development and Marketing” vertical as an Intern for Inmovidu Tech.

We found him to be a good team player besides being a hard worker. I hereby certify his work was satisfactory to the best of my knowledge.

We wish him success in his future endeavors.

Yours truly,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Anusha".

Ms. Anusha

HR Manager

InMovidu Technologies Private Limited

TO WHOM-SO-EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. MUHAMMED TAYIB SIDDIQUE, S/O Mr. SIDDIQUE, a student of BBA (Bachelor of business administration), SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, India\Mangalore has accomplished [Management of internship program]. Under the management of Mr. JALEEL (Manager of Quick Dwc) at Quick group LLC, from April /1/2021 To July/1/2021. We found him sincere, meticulous, and enthusiastic & result oriented. He worked well as a fragment of the team during the tenure. We take this prospect to thank him & wish him all the best for his future.

Awarded this [July-01-2021].

Mr. RIYAS

(HR MANAGER)

Head Office
Al Nahda, Sharjah
P.O. Box 65072
06 566 0687

Info@quickgroup.ae

AbleCold Logistics

Rathat Solutions Pvt. Ltd.

CIN - U74999KA2017PTC106056

Email - enquiries@ablecold.com

Phone - +91-9884093456

Website - www.ablecold.com

#271, First Floor, 14th Cross, Opp. Indiranagar Park,
Indiranagar, Bengaluru - 560038, Karnataka

AbleCold

06th July 2021

To,

Prasad S Kudtarkar

Bengaluru

SUB: INTERNSHIP COMPLETION LETTER

We are glad to inform you that Prasad S Kudtarkar has successfully completed his internship at AbleCold Logistics from 20th March 2021 to 20th June 2021

During his internship, he worked on Demand and Supply Chain .

We found him hard working, willing to learn and good in communication.

Abhay Kothari

With Best Regards,

Abhay Kothari

Founder

Rathat Solutions Private Limited

Date: 30th June, 2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr Haggai Titus, has done his internship in Content Writer as an Associate Content Writer at Gloify, Bengaluru from 15th March 2021 to 30th June 2021.

During the internship he demonstrated good skills with a self-motivated attitude to learn new things. His performance exceeded expectations and was able to complete the task successfully ontime.

We wish you all the best for your near future.

Thanking You

Experience cum Relieving Certificate

To,
Yahya Mohammed Yakub
Bangalore

This is to certify that **Yahya Mohammed Yakub**, employed with **Zolostays Property Solutions Pvt. Ltd.** has been relieved from the services of the company at the close of the working hours on 7 May 2022. Here are the details of the employment:

Name of the Department	College Demand
Employee Code	ZSIN00471
Last Designation Held	Intern
Date of Joining	24 January 2022
Date of Leaving	7 May 2022

In case of any queries, please feel free to reach out to hr@zolostays.com

Yours faithfully,
For Zolostays Property Solutions Pvt. Ltd.

Ramesh Nair
Associate Director - Human Resources
Date: 7 May 2022
Place: Bangalore

ZOLOSTAYS PROPERTY SOLUTIONS PRIVATE LIMITED

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

YENEPOYA MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL

(A CONSTITUENT COLLEGE OF YENEPOYA (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY), Recognised under Sec 3 (A) of the UGC Act, 1956)
Accredited by NAAC with 'A' Grade

University Road, Deralakatte, Mangalore - 575 018. Ph. : 2204668 / 69 / 70, Fax : 0824 - 2202193

Certificate No. H-2019-2020
March 01, 2019 - March 30, 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Muhammad Hashir M** a BHA student of Srinivas College, Pandeshwar, Mangalore has successfully completed 3 month posting in our organization under the guidance of Dr. Sunita Saldanha, Professor & HOD, Department of Hospital Administration, Yenepoya (Deemed to be University) from 09.01.2022 to 09.04.2022. His performance and conduct during the project period was good.

Date: 18.04.2022

Place: Deralakatte, Mangalore.

Professor & HOD
Dept. of Hospital Administration
Professor & HOD
Dept. of Hospital Administration

**GROUP OF ANOTHER SIDE OF
HUMAN RESOURCE
CAREER TRAINING AND JOB PLACEMENT**

Date: 10/05/2022

This is certifying that Mr. Rohith has worked with as a Human Resource Assistant from 18th January 2022 till 30th of April 2022 and Successfully Completed his Internship of 75days

In this period, hr has shown full Sincerity, Dedication and Hard work towards his concerned job, which has helped in improving the management of the company.

This is to inform that Rohith has been relieved from allof his duties. I wish him good luck and great future ahead.

Thanking you

For **GROUP OF ANOTHER SIDE OF
HUMAN RESOURCE**

Proprietor

Group of Another side of human Resource

AMARDEEP TRADERS

K.V.S.S. Bank, Building
Kavoor Post, Mangalore - 575 015
Karnataka

Ph: (01) 9824-2482003

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Miss K.Krithi (REG NO 25U19F5002) is a BBA Student Dean College of Management & Commerce of Srinivas University Mangaluru, has completed the "Internship Training" in our company from 15th January 2022 - 30th April 2022.

During the course of the project work she had shown keen interest in learning about our organization and submitted a copy a study report and is found original.

We wish all the best in her future Endeavour.

Date: 25.04.2022

Place: Kavoor, Mangalore

For Amardeep Traders

KRISHNA ENTERPRISES
Kavoor, Traders, Kavoor Junction
MANGALORE-15

30/04/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. Swathi J Bangera (Reg No: 2SU19FS004), Final Year Student of BBA Financial Services from Srinivas University College Of Management And Commerce Mangalore, has Successfully Completed her Internship Under HR Activities at MAX HYPERMARKET INDIA PVT.LTD. (SPAR_Forum Mall) MANGALORE from 15/01/2022 to 30/04/2022.

We found her sincere, hardworking, and technically sound and result oriented. She worked well as part of a team during her tenure.

We wish her All the Best in her future endeavors.

For Max Hypermarket India Pvt. Ltd.

Snigdha Raj
Ex. Business HR

 LANDMARK
GROUP

MAX HYPERMARKET INDIA PVT. LTD.
GP 29A30, No 19-B-46429
Forum Mall, Magaleswari Temple Road
Attavar Village, Cantonment Ward
Panshalpet,
Mangalore-575021
PHONE: +91-824-2488122
WEBSITE: www.sparindia.com
CIN U52190KA2004PTC037768

AMARDEEP TRADERS

K.V.S.S. Bank, Building
Kavoor Post, Mangalore - 575 015
Karnataka

Ph: (0) 0824-2482033

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Miss Yashwitha PK (REG NO 25U19FS006) is a BBA Student Dean College of Management & Commerce of Srinivas University Mangaluru, has completed the "Internship Training" in our company from 15th January 2022 - 30th April 2022.

During the course of the project work she had shown keen interest in learning about our organization and submitted a copy a study report and is found original.

We wish all the best in her future Endeavour.

Date: 25.04.2022

Place: Kavoor, Mangalore

For Amardeep Traders

AMARDEEP ENTERPRISES
Kavoor Post, Mangalore - 575 015
KARNATAKA

بريدج وي للأنظمة الطبية ذ.م.م.
Bridgeway Medical Systems L.L.C.

Ref. no: 001/INT-BMS/2022

26th April 2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms. Liya Mirza S K, Bachelor of Hospital Administration student of Srinivas College of Management and Commerce, Mangalore, Karnataka, India has successfully completed her two months Human Resource Internship (20TH February to 20th April ,2022) in our organization working with the Human Resource department.

Thanking you.

Aaliya Ashraf
Asst. Manager – HR

Post Box: 50066, 1st floor, Al Ashram Bldg., Garhoud, Dubai - UAE

+971 4 282 2890

+971 4 256 6052

healthcare@bridgeway.ae

www.bridgewayhealthcare.com

INDIA • MIDDLE EAST • AFRICA

KASTURBA HOSPITAL

MANIPAL

(An Associate Hospital of MAHE, Manipal)

30th April 2022

TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to confirm that, **Mr. Shahinsha K** (Reg No-2SU19HA004) BBA student, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru has undergone an Internship training at various departments of Operations under the guidance of Mr. Jibu Thomas, Chief Manager-Operations, Kasturba Hospital, Manipal during the month of February to April 2022.

During this period, we found Mr. Shahinsha to be dedicated and committed towards his training and we wish him all the success in his future endeavors.

Medical Superintendent

Post Box No. 7, Manipal-576104, Karnataka, India. Phone +91 - 820 - 2571201 - 2571210 (10 lines)
Fax : +91 - 820 - 2571934. Email : office_kh@manipal.edu

MR 447

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ISO 45001:2018

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KAN/RZ/S8212/06/2022/22

Date: 09/06/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Adithya S Reg. No. 2SU19HN005 pursuing Bachelors in Business Administration (BBA) from Srinivas University Mangalore. Has successfully completed his Internship in Customer Support and Service from CR Department from M/s. Kanchana Automobiles Private Limited, Mangalore. (Dealer for Hyundai Motors India Limited dealing with Hyundai Passenger Cars) from 06-01-2022 to 05-04-2022.

During his training, we found him to be sincere, dedicated, committed and hardworking.

Team Kanchana wishes him good luck and all the very best for his future endeavor.

For Kanchana Automobiles Pvt Ltd

FOR HEAD HR

09/06/22

[Head – HR & Admin]
KANCHANA AUTOMOBILES PVT LTD

Darul basara ,ajjandka, k.c road ,mangalore-22

CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. AHMED ASHYAM AZAD J (Reg no. 2SU19HN007), Final year BBA student of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE as successfully completed his internship project title "A STUDY ON PREFERENCES IN DIGITAL MARKETING" During the period Jan 1st 2022 To march 30th 2022 at our organization oxyeblue, Mangalore.

We found into sincere and hardworking during the course of internship with us

"We wish him all the success in his future endeavors"

[Managing partner]

Candidate signature

29th June 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

INTERNSHIP CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Ms. AMINA SUHA ISHAQUE (Reg. No. 2SU19HN009)** student at SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY Pandeshwara, Mangalore-575001 has successfully completed her internship at Prestige Mangalore Retail Ventures Pvt. Ltd. from 28th January 2022 – 28th April 2022 (3 Months) and submitted project report for the same.

We found her sincere & hardworking while undergoing project work.

We wish her best of luck in his future endeavors.

Yours sincerely

For and on behalf of Prestige Mangalore Retail Ventures Private Limited.

Arvind Shrivastav
Centre Head

Registered Office: Prestige Mangalore Retail Ventures Private Limited,
Prestige Falcon Tower, No. 19, Brunton Road, Bengaluru 560 025
Karnataka

Local Office: 4th Floor, Centre Management Office, Mangaladevi road, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore -575001.

IN: U452DOTG2004PTCP44794

T: +91 0824-2498498 R: infodesk.fizamalls@nexusmalls.com

F: www.nexusmalls.com

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

	प्रधान कार्यालय, लोकमंगल, 1501, शिवाजीनगर, पुणे-5 Head Office: LOKMANGAL, 1501, SHIVA JINAGAR, PUNE - 5	

Ref. No.	AG16/Project/Lana/2022-23	Date	17.06.2022
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CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to Certify that Ms. LANA IKA SUCHIANG (Reg No: 2SU19HN015), final year BBA student of Institute of Management And Commerce SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY has done her project work "A STUDY ON LOANS /ADVANCES AND DEPOSITS WITH THE REFERENCE TO BANK OF MAHARASHTRA, MANGALORE" during the period of three months from 31th DECEMBER 2021 to 31th MARCH 2022 under the guidance of Mr. SUCHETH M D' SOUZA, Chief Manager, BANK OF MAHARASHTRA, MANGALORE BRANCH.

"We wish her all the success in her future endeavours"

For

Bank of Maharashtra महाराष्ट्र
For Bank of Maharashtra

for.
Chief Manager / मंगलूरु
Branch Manager / Mangalore
Mangalore Branch

YENEPOYA

(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Recognised under Sec. 3(A) of the UGC Act 1956
Accredited by NAAC with 'A' Grade

YU/REG/HRD/04076/Certificate/2022

27.05.2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Manikandan (Reg.No 2SU19HN016) IIIrd BBA (Honours) in Srinivas College of Management and Commerce has completed internship in the department of Human Resource at Yenepoya (Deemed to be University) from 20.01.2022 to 28.02.2022.

REGISTRAR

Registrar
Yenepoya (Deemed to be University)
University Road, Durgamachari
Mangalagiri - 575 918

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

KERALA STATE RUBBER CO-OPERATIVE LTD

Rubco House, South Bazar, Kannur-670 002, Kerala, India
Ph. 91-497-2709749, 2711134, 2711378, Fax: 91-497-2711030
Website: www.rubcogroup.com, E-mail: info@rubcomail.com

No: A&P/INT/Q-212

Date : 23rd May 2022.

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms. Medha P V (Reg.No.2SU19HN017), BBA student of Management and Commerce City Campus, Mangalore, Srinivas University has successfully completed her Project "A Study on Effectiveness of Performance Appraisal at Rubco Huat Wood, Kannur" in our Organization for a Period of Three Months commencing from 17.01.2022 to 16.04.2022. She has completed the Project satisfactorily.

We wish all the best in her careers.

For Kerala State Rubber Co-operative Ltd.,

General Manager (HR) i/c.

ZAIN MOTORS

Authorised Dealer for Bajaj Auto Limited
GSTIN : 32AJJPM1117A1Z0

Date : 10-05-2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. MOHAMMAD NIHAL S/o Mr. MOHAMMED IQBAL** as a student of **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE, CITY CAMPUS, PANDESHWAR, MANGALORE** for the award of **BACHELOR DEGREE IN BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION (B.B.A)** having **REG. NO. 2SU19HN018** has undergone his Internship in our organization as a part of his project.

During his tenure of three month from 19-01-2022 to 18-04-2022 , we found **Mr. MOHAMMAD NIHAL** to be Hard Working, Conscientious, Dedicated and responsible in study and we wish his all the best in future.

For ZAIN MOTORS

FOR ZAIN MOTORS

General Manager
General Manager

AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL TOURS & TRAVELS, HAJJ & UMRAH

2nd floor, Meepiri Centre, Kumbala. Ph: 04998-217277 Mob: 9895064777, 9744647786
E-mail: alfalah.intl77@gmail.com, www.alfalahintl.com

Ref.

Date: 22/04/2022.....

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr MOHAMMED NAZWAN [2SU19HN020]**, STUDENT OF **INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, CITY CAMPUS PANDESHWARA , MANGALORE**, has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of Finance from **29/01/2022** to **21/04/2022** under the guidance of **Mr SUBAIR SA (MANAGER)**.

During the period of his internship program with us he had been exposed to different process was found punctual, hardworking and inquisitive.

We wish him every success in his life and career.

For **AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL**

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

Darul basra aijanadka, K.C Road, kotekar, Mangalore -22

DATE: 30-03-2022

CRETIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. MOHAMMED SHIAHAN (Reg no. 2SU19HN023), final year BBA student of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE has successfully completed his internship project titled "A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS OXYEBLUE ,MANGALORE" during the period Jan 1st 2022 to March 30th 2022 at our organization- OXYEBLUE ,MANGALORE .

We found him to be sincere and hardworking during the course of internship with us

"We wish him all the success in his future endeavors"

[Managing partner]

Candidate signature

AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL TOURS & TRAVELS, HAJJ & UMRAH

2nd floor, Meepiri Centre, Kumbala. Ph: 04998-217277 Mob: 9895064777, 9744647785
E-mail: alfalah.intl77@gmail.com, www.alfalahintl.com

Ref.

Date: 22/04/2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr MOOSA MUHAZ [2SU19HN025], STUDENT OF INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, CITY CAMPUS PANDESHWARA, MANGALORE, has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of Sales and marketing from 29/01/2022 to 21/04/2022 under the guidance of Mr SUBAIR SA (MANAGER),

During the period of his internship program with us he had been exposed to different process was found punctual, hardworking and inquisitive.

We wish him every success in his life and career.

For AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is certify that Mr MUHAMMED SANAD C.A (25U19HN027), STUDENT OF INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, CITY CAMPUS PANDESHWARA MANGALORE, has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of Sales and marketing from 29/01/2022 to 21/04/2022 under the guidance of Mrs SINDHU(MANAGER) During the period of his internship program with us he had been exposed to different Process was found punctual, handworking and inquisitive

We wish him every success in his life and career

For ARTIC MOTORS

AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL TOURS & TRAVELS, HAJJ & UMRAH

2nd floor, Meepiri Centre, Kumbala. Ph: 04998-217277 Mob: 9895064777, 9744647786
E-mail: alfalah.intl77@gmail.com, www.alfalahintl.com

Ref.

Date 22/04/2022.....

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr.SAHAD M.A[2SU19HN029],STUDENT OF INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT &COMMERCE SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY,CITY CAMPUS PANDESHWARA, MANGALORE, has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of sales and marketing from 29/01/2022 to 21/04/2022 under the guidance of Mr.SUBAIR SA(MANAGER),

During the period of his internship program with us he had been exposed to different process was found punctual, hardworking and inquisitive.

We wish him every success in his life and career.

For AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL

REF: MANG/HRD/3593/2022-23

DATE: 24/05/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. SATHWIK SHETTY**, student of Bachelor of Business Administration, 2SU19HN030, Srinivasa College of Management and Commerce, Mangalore. He completed his Internship towards the partial fulfillment of the requirements for the course of Bachelor Of Business Administration [BBA] in our organization.

He has worked as an Intern from **01st January 2022 to 31st March 2022** and submitted study report with reference to **Advertisement Management with reference to Mandovi Motors Private Limited, Mangalore.**

This certificate is issued on request of the student as support document to be furnish along with project report.

We wish him good luck.

For Mandovi Motors Private Limited.,

For **MANDOVI MOTORS PRIVATE LIMITED**
RAJESH BHAT M
A.M. - HUMAN RESOURCES
HR Manager

Arvind Building, Dr. Shivarama Karantha Road, Hampankatta, Mangaluru - 575001.

Ph.:Sales: 0824-2410128, Mob.: 9980180128 | Website: www.mandovimotors.in | Email: agmsales@mandovi.net

GST NO: 29AACCM4309H1ZI PAN: AACCM4309H CIN: U34300KA1999PTC024799

YENEPOYA
(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)
Recognised under Sec. 3(A) of the UGC Act 1956
Accredited by NAAC with 'A' Grade

U/REG/HRD/04050/Certificate/2022

23.05.2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. Saramma Sehala (Reg.No 2SU19HN031) IIIrd BA (Honours) in Srinivas College of Management and Commerce has completed internship in the department of Human Resource at Yenepoya (Deemed to be University) from 20.01.2022 to 26.03.2022.

S. S. Srinivasan

REGISTRAR

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

AL- FALAH INTERNATIONAL TOURS & TRAVELS, HAJJ & UMRAH

2nd floor, Meepiri Centre, Kumbala. Ph: 04998-217277 Mob: 9895064777, 9744647786
E-mail: alfalahlnti77@gmail.com, www.alfalahintl.com

Ref.

Date: 22/04/2022.....

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr SYED IBRAHIM AFRAD [2SU19HN033], STUDENT OF INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, CITY CAMPUS PANDESHWARA , MANGALORE, has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of Sales and marketing from 29/01/2022 to 21/04/2022 under the guidance of Mr SUBAIR SA (MANAGER),

During the period of his internship program with us he had been exposed to different process was found punctual, hardworking and inquisitive.

We wish him every success in his life and career.

For AL-FALAH INTERNATIONAL

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

☎ 8891 000 085 0487 2704076
📍 KL Abdul Sathar Impex Pvt. Ltd.
Near Makkani, South Bazar
Kannur Kerala - 570002
✉ info@klobdusathar.com
🌐 www.klobdusathar.com

This is to certify that Mr. AKASH SAJITH (Reg No.2SU19LS007) student of Srinivas College of Management and Commerce ,Pandeshwar, Mangalore has completed his internship on " A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF RETAIL MARKETING STRATEGY OF KL-ABDUL SATHR IMPEX Pvt.Ltd., South Bazar, Kannur" during the period of 04.03.2022 to 01.04.2022, in partial fulfillment of the requirement of the Degree in Bachelor of Business Administration in Logistics and supply chain management.

He was very keen interested, well-mannered and enthusiastic during the period of training.

Abdul Sathar

For KL ABDUL SATHAR IMPEX PVT. LTD.

Round Logs, Timber, Plywoods, Veneers, Laminates, Hardware & Interior Decorative Products

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. ADHISH M** (Reg. No. 2SU19LS003) of Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed his Internship project titled " **A Study on Shipping Functions** " at **AMOGHA LOGISTICS** , Mangalore during the period from **15th January to 15th April 2022**.

During the tenure of the Project work he has been very keen & resourceful.

Wishing him all the best in his future endeavours.

for **AMOGHA LOGISTICS**

PARTNER

DATE: 29.04.2022
PLACE : MANGALORE

1st Floor, Sri Ram Building, Kottara Chowki, Mangalore - 575006, Karnataka, India.

Web : www.amoghagroup.com

Manipal Technologies Limited

MTL/HRTA/2122/0014

9th June, 2022

To Whomsoever It May Concern

Subject: Internship Completion certificate for Mr. B.M. Dhanush (Reg No: 25U19LS012)

Dear Sir/Madam

We hereby state on record that Mr. B.M. Dhanush (Reg No: 25U19LS012) has completed an internship project in our Logistics Department of Manipal Technologies Limited, Manipal from 9th May, 2022 to 9th June, 2022 under the guidance of Mr. Sree S A Kumar, Head Logistics.

During this period of internship, Mr. B.M. Dhanush (Reg No: 25U19LS012) has successfully met the objectives of the internship as set at the beginning of the internship. We found him hard working and resourceful.

We wish Mr. B.M. Dhanush (Reg No: 25U19LS012) all success in his future endeavors.

Thanking you
Yours Sincerely

Nagaprasad Shettigar
Assistant Manager - HR

Manipal Technologies Limited

Head Office: 10th & 21st Building, Prestige Tower, Manipal, 576104, Karnataka, India
City: 08229-444200/444200/444200
Tel: +91 822 2701001 - 91 822 4275600 Fax: +91 822 2708001
e-mail: info@manipaltechnologies.com web: www.manipaltechnologies.com

Doc: 00000

KASTURBA HOSPITAL
MANIPAL
(An associate Hospital of MAHE, Manipal)

30th April 2022

TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to confirm that, **Mr. Muhammed Mufeed B P** (Reg No-2SU19LS021), BBA student, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru has undergone an Internship training at various departments of Operations under the guidance of Mr. Jibu Thomas, Chief Manager-Operations, Kasturba Hospital, Manipal during the month of February to April 2022.

During this period, we found Mr. Muhammed Mufeed to be dedicated and committed towards his training and we wish him all the success in his future endeavors.

Medical Superintendent

Post Box No. 7, Manipal-576104, Karnataka, India. Phone : +91 - 820 - 2571201 - 2571210 (10 lines)
Fax : +91 - 820 - 2571934. Email : office.kh@manipal.edu

Sudeep

MR 447

ISO 9001:2015
ISO 14001:2015
ISO 45001:2011

Om Sai Logistics

Near Cargo Gate, Bala Post, Mangalore - 575 030 D.K.
Email: omsalogsitics2015@gmail.com

Phone: 7488813222
8310418473

GSTIN: 29AYKPB8413C1ZM

DATE: 07/04/2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that (Ms/Mr /Mrs. Dancy D'souza student of Shrinivas University Mangalore has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of 3 months internship from January to March under guidance of Logistics and Supply Chain Management.

During the period of her/ his internship program with us, she/ he had been exposed to different processes and was found diligent, hardworking and inquisitive.

We wish her/ him every success in her/his life and career.

Shailaja
For Om Sai Logistics

Proprietor

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

CAPEX

Kerala State Cashew Workers Apex
Industrial Co-operative Society Ltd.

P. B. No. 262, Industrial Development Plot

H & C Compound, Mundakkal West, Kollam 691 001

Reg No. IND (ST) 12

Phone : 0474 - 2742499, 2765644

FAX - 0474-2747153

email : cashewcapex@rediffmail.com

website : www.cashewcapex.com

15.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr.Raj Mohan, {Reg.No.2SU19LS025} B.B.A {Logistics and Supply Chain Management} student** of Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka has completed "AN INTERNSHIP PROGRAMME AT CAPEX" from 12.01.2022 to 31.03.2022. He has completed the Internship programme satisfactorily. During his association with us, he was very keen and enthusiastic in his work.

We wish him all the best in future endeavors.

Managing Director

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

CAPEX

Kerala State Cashew Workers Apex
Industrial Co-operative Society Ltd.

P. B. No. 262, Industrial Development Plot
H & C Compound, Mundakkal West, Kollam 691 001
Reg No. IND (ST) 12
Phone : 0474 - 2742499, 2765644
FAX - 0474-2747153

email : cashewcapex@rediffmail.com
website : www.cashewcapex.com

15.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr.Raj Mohan, {Reg.No.2SU19LS025} B.B.A {Logistics and Supply Chain Management} student** of Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka has completed "AN INTERNSHIP PROGRAMME AT CAPEX" from 12.01.2022 to 31.03.2022. He has completed the Internship programme satisfactorily. During his association with us, he was very keen and enthusiastic in his work.

We wish him all the best in future endeavors.

Managing Director

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

Kerala State Cashew Workers Apex
Industrial Co-operative Society Ltd.

P. B. No. 262, Industrial Development Plot
H & C Compound, Mundakkal West, Kollam 691 001
Reg No. IND (ST) 12
Phone : 0474 - 2742499, 2765644
FAX - 0474-2747153

email : cashewcapex@rediffmail.com
website : www.cashewcapex.com

15.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Abhinav Chandran, {Reg.No.2SU19LS002}**
B.B.A {Logistics and Supply Chain Management} student of Srinivas
University, Mangaluru, Karnataka has completed "AN INTERNSHIP
PROGRAMME AT CAPEX" from 12.01.2022 to 31.03.2022. He has
completed the Internship programme satisfactorily. During his association
with us, he was very keen and enthusiastic in his work.

We wish him all the best in future endeavors.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'S. M. 12'.

Managing Director

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

COCHIN INTERNATIONAL CONTAINER FREIGHT STATION

Unit of Kerala State Industrial Enterprises Limited (KSIE)

(A Government of Kerala Undertaking)

Anavathi Junction, Container Road, Eloor, Udyogamandal P.O.

Phone: +91-484-2557255, 2556255, Fax: +91-484-2557255, E-mail: cicfs.ksie@gmail.com

KSIE/CFS/685

20.05.2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. SIDHIKUL AKBAR S (Reg No. 2SU19LS028), Student of Srinivas University College of Management and Commerce, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore-575001, undergoing BBA Logistics management has completed his Internship Programme at Cochin International Container Freight Station, a unit of Kerala State Industrial Enterprises Ltd. (a Govt. of Kerala undertaking), for a period from 15th February 2022 to 14th March 2022 as a part of his curriculum.

During this period, his character and conduct were found to be good.

For Cochin International Container Freight Station

General Manager

Head Office
Thiruvananthapuram
PIN - 695 008
Tel: 0471-2324159, 2326913
Fax: 0471-2334590

Trivandrum Air Cargo Terminal
(ISO 9001:2000 Certified)
Trivandrum - 695 008
Tel: 0471-2501016, 2501031
Fax: 2504870

Calicut Air Cargo Complex
(ISO 9001:2000 Certified)
Kariapur - 673 647
Tel: 0483-2710044, 2711765
Fax: 2713206

Kerala Soaps
Kozhikode
Kozhikode - 673 011
Tel: 0495-2762559
Fax: 0495-2762455

E-com portal
www.keralacode.com

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

CAPEX

Kerala State Cashew Workers Apex
Industrial Co-operative Society Ltd.

P. B. No. 262, Industrial Development Plot
H & C Compound, Mundakkal West, Kollam 691 001
Reg No. IND (ST) 12
Phone : 0474 - 2742499, 2765644
FAX - 0474-2747153

email : cashewcapex@rediffmail.com
website : www.cashewcapex.com

15.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Abhinav Chandran, {Reg.No.2SU19LS002}**
B.B.A {Logistics and Supply Chain Management} student of Srinivas
University, Mangaluru, Karnataka has completed "AN INTERNSHIP
PROGRAMME AT CAPEX" from 12.01.2022 to 31.03.2022. He has
completed the Internship programme satisfactorily. During his association
with us, he was very keen and enthusiastic in his work.

We wish him all the best in future endeavors.

Managing Director

Om Sai Logistics

Near Cargo Gate, Bale Post, Mangalore -575 030 D.K.
Email: omsalogs2015@gmail.com

Phone: 7406913222
8310419473

GSTIN: 29AYKPB8413C1ZM

DATE: 07/04/2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that (Ms/Mr /Mrs. Dancy D'souza student of Shrinivas University Mangalore has successfully completed a summer internship in the field of 3 months internship from January to March under guidance of Logistics and Supply Chain Management.

During the period of her/ his internship program with us, she/ he had been exposed to different processes and was found diligent, hardworking and inquisitive.

We wish her/ him every success in her/his life and career.

Shailaja
For Om Sai Logistics

Proprietor

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

यातायात प्रबंधक का कार्यालय
Office of the Traffic Manager
मिडिलगाइन आईलैंड, कोच्चिन - 682 004
WILINGDON ISLAND, COCHIN - 682 004
दूरभाष/Phone : +91 (484) 2888418 258 2200
फैक्स/Fax : +91 (484) 2888418
ई-मेल/Email : tm@cochinport.gov.in
वेबसाइट/Website : www.cochinport.gov.in

Date: 18.02.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. AKASH S PANIKAR (Reg. No: 2SU19LS006) student of Srinivas College of Management and Commerce, Pandeshwar, Mangalore has completed his internship on "Organizational study of Cochin Port Trust" during the period from 20.01.2022 to 18.02.2022, in partial fulfillment of the requirement of the Degree in Bachelor of Business Administration in Logistics and Supply Chain Management).

ANIL KUMAR D
Deputy Traffic Manager

Follow us on Twitter cochin_port

COMPANY CERTIFICATE:

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಪ್ರಾಧಿಕಾರ
नव मंगलूर पत्तन प्राधिकरण
NEW MANGALORE PORT AUTHORITY
(Fully Solar Powered)

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping & Waterways)
ಪಣಬುರು ಪಂಚಾಯ್ತು Panambur/ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಗಲೂರ Mangalore- 575010

No. NMPT/DTM (O)/2022

20.06.2022

Dy. Manager
Corp. Relations & Communications,
General Administration Dept.
New Mangalore Port Authority

This is to inform that **Jb. Muhammed Sahshad Manjoor** from SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY successfully completed internship for the stipulated period at NMPA on Port Operations and Management with special emphasis on Warehousing and Containerization. During the period of study, exposure on various aspects of Port Operations and management viz. Bulk/Liquid/Container Operations and Global Shipping and Logistics Supply Chain has been provided. This report effectively captures the understanding of the subject and is hereby endorsed and certified.

Digitally signed
by Gokul R
Date: 2022.06.20
'11:48:40 +05'30

R. Gokul
Deputy Traffic Manager (Operations)

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

COCHIN INTERNATIONAL CONTAINER FREIGHT STATION
Unit of Kerala State Industrial Enterprises Limited (KSIE)
(A Government of Kerala Undertaking)
Anavathi Junction, Container Road, Eloor, Udyogamandal P.O.
Phone: +91-484-2557255, 2556255, Fax: +91-484-2557255, E-mail: cicfs ksie@gmail.com

KSIE/CFS/685

20.05.2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. SIDHIKUL AKBAR S (Reg No. 2SU19LS028), Student of Srinivas University College of Management and Commerce, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore-575001, undergoing BBA Logistics management has completed his Internship Programme at Cochin International Container Freight Station, a unit of Kerala State Industrial Enterprises Ltd. (a Govt. of Kerala undertaking), for a period from 15th February 2022 to 14th March 2022 as a part of his curriculum.

During this period, his character and conduct were found to be good.

For Cochin International Container Freight Station

General Manager

Head Office
Thiruvananthapuram
PIN - 695 008
Tel: 0471-2324159, 2326913
Fax: 0471-2334590

Trivandrum Air Cargo Terminal
(ISO 9001:2000 Certified)
Trivandrum - 695 008
Tel: 0471-2501018, 2501031
Fax: 2504870

Calicut Air Cargo Complex
(ISO 9001:2000 Certified)
Kannur - 673 847
Tel: 0483-2710044, 2711765
Fax: 2713206

Kerala Branch
Kozhikode
Kozhikode - 673 011
Tel: 0495-2762555
Fax: 0495-2762455

E-com portal
www.keralacife.com

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. SHIVARATHNAPRASAD P.** (Reg. No. **2SU19LS027**) of Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed his Internship project titled "**A Study on Cargo Handling System**" at **AMOGHA LOGISTICS**, Mangalore during the period from **15th January to 15th April 2022**.

During the tenure of the Project work, he has been very keen & resourceful.

Wishing him all the best in his future endeavours.

for **AMOGHA LOGISTICS**

PARTNER

DATE: 29.04.2022
PLACE : MANGALORE

1st Floor, Sri Ram Building, Kottara Chowki, Mangalore - 575006, Karnataka, India.

Web : www.amoghagroup.com

कोचिन पत्तन प्राधिकरण
COCHIN PORT AUTHORITY

यातायात विभाग

TRAFFIC DEPARTMENT
Willingdon Island, Cochin – 682 009
Phone: +91 (484) 2582200
Fax: +91 (484) 2666418
e-mail: tm@cochinport.gov.in
www.cochinport.gov.in

Date: 12.04.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Adith V.O (Reg.No:2SU19LS004) student of Srinivas College of Management and Commerce, Pandeshwar, Mangalore has completed his internship on “Organizational study on Cochin Port Authority” during the period from 01.02.2022 to 03.03.2022, in partial fulfillment of the requirement of the Degree in Bachelor of Business Administration in Logistics and Supply Chain Management.

12/4/2022
ANIL KUMAR D
Deputy Traffic Manager

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

E-mail : shetty.nagarajb@ganeshshipping.com
karthikshetty@ganeshshipping.com
agency@ganeshshipping.com
export@ganeshshipping.com
import@ganeshshipping.com
accounts@ganeshshipping.com

PHONE OFF : 0824-2458429 / 2459219
2459229 / 2458489
Res : 2211189 / 2213442
FAX : 0824 - 2458903

SRI GANESH SHIPPING AGENCY

KANARA TOWERS
KOTTARA CHOWKI, MANGALORE - 575 006, INDIA
GSTIN : 29AAFFS2694K1ZK

To Whomsoever It May Concern

This is to Certify that Mr. Akhilesh P – Final Year BBA (LS & SCM) student at Srinivas University (College of Management and commerce), Mangalore, bearing Reg No: 2SU19LS008 has undergone internship training in "A Study on shipping activities & logistics" with reference to Sri Ganesh Shipping Agency, Mangalore from 3RD January 2022 to 3rd April 2022.

During this period he was found to be sincere, co-operative and hardworking. His character and conduct was good.

We wish him all the best and success in all his future endeavors.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 04.04.2022

B. Nagaraj Shetty

(Mg. Partner)

B. NAGARAJA SHETTY
Managing Partner
Sri Ganesh Shipping Agency, Mangalore

H.O. : Mangalore. Branches : Bangalore • Karwar • Goa
Our Services : Steamer Agency; C&F; Transportation; C.H.A; Stevedoring; Logistics - Project Cargo

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

KERALA STATE RUBBER CO-OPERATIVE LTD.

(HAWAI CHAPPAL FACTORY)

Rubco Industrial Complex, Vallyavelicham, Mooriyad P.O, Kuthuparamba, Kannur
Kerala, India-670 643, Phone: +91 490 2364824, Telefax: +91 490 2364822
E-mail:hawai@rubcogroup.com, Web: www.rubcogroup.com

Ref No: RUB/RIC/A&P/IP/CER 15/2021-2022

18.05.2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Abhishek Mohan (Reg No.2SU19LS001)** student of Srinivas College of Management and Commerce, Pandeshwar, Mangalore has completed his internship on "A STUDY ON INFLUENCE OF SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT WITH INTRODUCTION OF SUB DEALERS IN THE MATTRESS MARKET OF RUBCO, KANNUR" during the period of 04.03.2022 to 08.04.2022, in partial fulfillment of the requirement of the Degree in Bachelor of Business Administration in Logistics and supply chain management.

For Kerala State Rubber Co. Oppltd
For Kerala state Rubber Co. Oppltd
[Signature]
Factory Manager (RIC)
Factory Manager (RIC)

Head Off : Rubco House, South Bazar, Kannur-670 002, Kerala State, India.
Phone: 91-497 2709749, 2701908 Fax: 91-497 - 2711030
Website : www.rubcogroup.com E-mail: info@rubcogroup.com

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

Main Road, Kanhangad - 571315
Kasaragod Dist Kerala India
Phone - 91467 220 4019
email: traveltimekhd@gmail.com

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MY CONCERN

This is to certify the MR. ANIRUDH. P (2su19LS010) Student of SRINIVAS COLLAGE OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE (Branch : BBA LOGISTICS) has successfully completed 07/02/2022 to 08/04/2022 (60 days) internship program at TRAVEL TIME TOURS KANHANGAD

During this period, he has shown time keeping and Interest in learning various aspects of connected with his academic requirement and was found the obedient as well as industrious.

AJMAL MOHAMMED
MANAGING DIRRECTOR
7560857235

DATE:08-04-2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. NABEEL CH** (Reg. No. **2SU19LS023**) of Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed his Internship project titled "**A Study on Import and Export Process and Documentation** " at **AMOGHA SHIPPING AGENCY** , Mangalore during the period from **20th January to 10th April 2022**.

During the tenure of the Project work he has been very keen & resourceful.

Wishing him all the best in his future endeavours.

for **AMOGHA SHIPPING AGENCY**

PARTNER

DATE: 24.05.2022
PLACE : MANGALORE

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. HARSHAN T.V** (Reg. No. 2SU19LS017) of Sriwas University, Mangalore has successfully completed his Internship project titled "**A Study on Export Process and Documentation**" at **AMOGHA LOGISTICS, Mangalore** during the period from **15th January to 15th April 2022**.

During the tenure of the Project work he has been very keen & resourceful.

Wishing him all the best in his future endeavours.

for **AMOGHA LOGISTICS**

[Handwritten Signature]
PARTNER

DATE: 29.04.2022
PLACE : MANGALORE

1st Floor, Sri Ram Building, Kottara Chowki, Mangalore - 575006, Karnataka, India.

Web : www.amoghagroup.com

ಸಜ್ಜ ಪಂಚಲಕೂರು ಒಂದೆರು ಪಾಠಿಕೂರು
नव मंगलूर पत्तन प्राधिकरण
NEW MANGALORE PORT AUTHORITY
(Fully Solar Powered)

भारत सरकार (पत्तन पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping & Waterways)
ಪಂಚಲಕೂರು ಪಂಚಲಕೂರು Penambur/ಪಂಚಲಕೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರು Mangalore- 575010

No. NMPT/DTM (O)/2022

13.06.2022

Dy. Manager
Corp. Relations & Communications,
General Administration Dept.
New Mangalore Port Authority

This is to inform that **Jb. OMARUL FAROOQ PA** from SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE successfully completed internship for the stipulated period at NMPA on Port Operations and Management. During the period of study, exposure on various aspects of Port Operations and management viz. Bulk/Liquid/Container Operations and Global Shipping and Logistics Supply Chain has been provided. This report effectively captures the understanding of the subject and is hereby endorsed and certified.

Digitally signed
by Gokul R
Date:
2022.06.13
'15:59:20 +05'30

R. Gokul
Deputy Traffic Manager (Operations)

CERTIFICATE

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ (ಪತ್ತನ, ಪೊಟ ಪರಿವಹನ ಓರ ಜಲಮಾರ್ಗಿ ಮಂತ್ರಾಲಯ)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪನಾಬುರು ಪನಾಬುರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Aniketh V (USN No. 2SU19PM007) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Aniketh V
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಉಪ ಪ್ರಬಂಧಕ - ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಟ್ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪರ್ಕ
Dy Manager-Corporate Relations & Communication

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪನಾಬುರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ : 0824 - 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 -2408390

ಆರ್ಟಿಫಿಸಿಯಲ್ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 ಉರ್ದು ಅಂತರರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಅನುಪಾಲನಕರ್ತೃ ಪತ್ತನ
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಶಿಬಿರಾಲಯ: ಪಣಬುರ Panambur / ಕಛೇರಿ: ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Muhammed Siraj K K (USN No. 2SU19PM025) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Kandur
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट सम्बन्ध और संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust

पणबुर, मंगलूर - 575010

Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341

ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341

फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)

Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन

An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

नव मंगलूर बंदर न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (घटन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಶಿಬಿರಾಲಯ: ಪಾನ್‌ಬುರ್ Panambur / ಕಛೇರಿ: ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Aswin A S (USN No. 2SU19PM011)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Aswin A S
23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಉಪ ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕ - ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಷನ್ ರಿಲೇಷನ್ಸ್ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪರ್ಕ
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Communications)
ಶಿಬಿರಾಲಯ: ಪಾನ್‌ಬುರ್ Panambur
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಶಿಬಿರಾಲಯ: ಪಾನ್‌ಬುರ್ Panambur - 575010
ಶಿಬಿರಾಲಯ: ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

ಫೋನ್: 0824-2407341
0824-2408390

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ: 0824 - 2407341
0824 2408390

Phone Office 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax 0824 -2408390

ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 ಮತ್ತು ISO 45001:2018 ಅನ್ವಯದಲ್ಲಿ
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
नव मंगलूर पतन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಟ್ಟಣದ ಪಂಚಾಯ್ತು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 24.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Muhammed Shahin M M** (USN No. 2SU19PM024) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working
We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

for

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट सम्पर्क
Dy Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications
नव मंगलूर पतन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575 010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575 010

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824-2407341
फैक्स : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 -2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಾನ್‌ಬುರು ಪಂಚಾಯ್ತು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Jai Kumar Singh (USN No. 2SU19PM016) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Kackee
23/06/2022
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट मंत्रालय
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communication

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पानंबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ : 0824 - 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lir)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಣಂಬೂರು ಪಣಂಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 27.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Sulthan Sabeel Khan** (USN No. 2SU19PM032) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

[Signature]
27/06/2022
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक - कार्पोरेट रिलेशंस & कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager - Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणंबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ಡ್ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಂಚುರು ಪಣಬುರ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 24.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Muhammed Shahin M M (USN No. 2SU19PM024) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working
We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

for

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक - कॉर्पोरेट संबंध
Dy. Manager, Corporate Relations & Communications
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575 010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824-2407341
फैक्स : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 -2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

COMPANY CERTIFICATE (SCANNED CERTIFICATE)

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಫಣಬುರು ಪಣಬುರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Dheeraj (USN No. 2SU19PM015) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक - कॉर्पोरेट रिलेशंस & कम्युनिकेशन

Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Comm. Engagements

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

New Mangalore Port Trust

पणबुर्, मंगलूर - 575010

Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ (ಪತ್ತನ, ಪೊತ ಪರಿವಹನ ಔರ ಜಲಮಾರ್ಗ ಮಂತ್ರಾಲಯ)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಾಣಂಬೂರು ಪಣಂಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. K Benjamin John Simon** (USN No. 2SU19PM018) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Handwritten Signature)
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಉಪ ಪರಿವಹನ-ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಟ್ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪರ್ಕ
Dy. Manager Corporate Relations & Communications
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪಾಣಂಬೂರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore 575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ : 0824 - 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

ಆರ್‌ಐ‌ಎಸ್‌ಓ 9001 2015, 14001 2015 ಂದ್ ಆರ್‌ಐ‌ಎಸ್‌ಪಿಐಎಸ್ ಅನುಪಾಲನಕರ್ತಾ ಪತ್ತನ
An ISO 9001.2015, 14001.2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ (ಪತ್ತನ, ಪೊನ ಪರಿವಹನ ಔರ ಜಲಮಾರ್ಗ ಮಂತ್ರಾಲಯ)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಂಚೂರು ಪಣಬೂರು Panambur / ಪಂಚೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Aswin Pradeep I V** (USN No. 2SU19PM012) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Handwritten signature
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಉಪ ಪ್ರಬಂಧಕ-ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಟ್ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪರ್ಕ
Dy Manager-Corporate Relations & Communication
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪಂಚೂರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur Mangalore - 575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ 0824 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ 0824 2408390

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ 0824 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

Phone Office 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax 0824 - 2408390

ಆರ್ಟಿಎಸ್ಐ 9001 2015, 14001 2015 ಏವ್ ಆರ್ಟಿಎಸ್ಐಎಸ್ ಅನುಪಾಲನ ಕರ್ತೃ ಪತ್ತನ
An ISO 9001 2015, 14001 2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ: ಪಂಚಬುರ Panambur / ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ: ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Abdul Azeez V S (USN No. 2SU19PM002) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कॉर्पोरेट रिलेशंस एंड कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 -2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಣಬುರು ಪಣಬುರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Abinsha Nadir (USN No. 2SU19PM003)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट र्शणक एवं संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबुूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

दूरवाणी : कर्षीरि : 0824-2407341
फ़ोन : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फ़ैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Line)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಂಚೂರು ಪಣಬುರ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರ Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Adarsh U (USN No. 2SU19PM004) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Handwritten signature
23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट र्‌लेशंस एंड कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824-2407341
फैक्स : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

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Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

ಶ್ರೀನಿವಾಸ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ
ಬಿಬಿಎಸ್ (ಪೋರ್ಟ್, ಶಿಪಿಂಗ್ ಮ್ಯಾನೇಜ್‌ಮೆಂಟ್ & ಕಾಮರ್ಸ್)
ಸಿನ್ರಿವಾಸ್ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ
ಪಿ.ಎಂ.ಎಸ್.ಎಸ್.ಎಸ್. ಸಿಟಿ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575001

No.S/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.04.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Raghu A (USN No. 21SU19PM026) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 06.01.2022 to 06.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working. We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಶ್ರೀನಿವಾಸ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ
ಬಿಬಿಎಸ್ (ಪೋರ್ಟ್, ಶಿಪಿಂಗ್ ಮ್ಯಾನೇಜ್‌ಮೆಂಟ್ & ಕಾಮರ್ಸ್)
ಸಿನ್ರಿವಾಸ್ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ
ಪಿ.ಎಂ.ಎಸ್.ಎಸ್. ಸಿಟಿ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575001

ಕಾರ್ಯದರ್ಶಿ : 0824 2407361
0824 2408390

ಫೋನ್ : 0824 - 2407361
0824 - 2408390

ಫೋನ್ : 0824 - 2407361 (10 Lines)
ಫಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

ಮಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ ಪೋರ್ಟ್ ಟ್ರಸ್ಟ್
ಪಿ.ಎಂ.ಎಸ್.ಎಸ್. ಸಿಟಿ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575001

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಂಚುಬುರು ಪಂಚುಬುರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Mohammed Thoufeeq V B** (USN No. 2SU19PM021) student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce)** Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Handwritten Signature)
22/06/2022
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कॉर्पोरेट रिलेशंस एवं कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पंಚುಬುರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 -2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
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ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಒಳಗಡೆ: ಪಣಬುರ್ Panambur / ಮಂಡಳಿ: ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Shebin K (USN No. 2SU19PM030) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Handwritten signature
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट र्‌लेशंस एंव कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबुूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

दूरभाष : ०८२४-२४०७३४१
फैक्स : ०८२४-२४०८३९०

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : ०८२४ - २४०७३४१
फैक्स : ०८२४ - २४०८३९०

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ ९००१:२०१५, १४००१:२०१५ एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಂಚುರು ಪಣಮ್ಬುರ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರ Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Dhanush K (USN No. 2SU19PM014) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working. We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

23/06/2022
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ವಿಷಯ - ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಟ್ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ
Dy. Manager - Corp. Relations & Communications
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪಂಚುರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ : 0824 - 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

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भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಾಣಬೂರು ಪಣಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 20.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Shibin K S (USN No. 2SU19PM031) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.**

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
20/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-व्यापारिक सम्पर्क एवं संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

New Mangalore Port Trust

पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010

Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
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दूरभाष ; कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

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ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ (ಪತ್ತನ, ಛೊನ ಪರಿವಹನ ಔರ ಜಲಮಾರ್ಗ ಮಂತ್ರಾಲಯ)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಾಣಂಬೂರು ಪಣಮ್ಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 20.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Sanof K R (USN No. 2SU19PM029)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce)** Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.
We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Handwritten signature
20/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಉಪ ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕರು (ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಷನ್ ರಿಲೇಷನ್ಸ್ ಔರ ಕಮ್ಯುನಿಕೇಷನ್)
Dy. Manager (Corporate Relations & Communications)
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪಾಣಂಬೂರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

ದೂರಭಾಷೆ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ : 0824 - 2407341
ಫೇಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

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Fax : 0824 - 2408390

ಆರ್ಟಿಐಸಿಐ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 ಂವ್ ಆರ್ಟಿಐಸಿಐಐಸಿಐ ಅನುಪಾಲನಕರ್ತೃ ಪತ್ತನ
An ISO 9001 2015, 14001 2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

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भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

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ಪಾಣಬುರು ಪಣಬುರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

Date: 23.06.2022

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Sandeep S Pillai (USN No. 2SU19PM028) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working. We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट संपर्क एवं संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबुರು, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

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फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

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भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

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ಪಾಂಚೂರು ಪಣಂಬುರ / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರ ಮಂಗಲೂರ - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Asjoe Shajan (USN No. 2SU19PM010)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ನ್ಯೂ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Communications)
ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
New Mangalore Port Authority
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಚೇರಿ 0824-2407341
ತಾ. ಕಛೇರಿ 0824-2408390

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ 0824 - 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax 0824 2408390

ಸಾಟೈಸಮ್ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसओएस अनुरूपाननकर्ता पत्तन
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नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಂಚೂರು ಪಣಬ್ಬುರ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರ Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Mishal A M (USN No. 2SU19PM020)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.**

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट संपर्क एवं संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
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COMPANY CERTIFICATE

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಶಿಬಿರವು ಪಣಬುರ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 24.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Vishnu Vinod (USN No. 2SU19PM034)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.
We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट संबंध एवं संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
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आइएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
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SAGARMALA
PORT LET PROSPERITY

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Majesh M (USN No. 2SU19PM019)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप-प्रबन्धक (संस्था-संबन्धी सम्बन्ध और संचार)
Dy. Manager (Corporate Relations & Communications)

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पंಚುबुರ, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
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आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

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No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 27.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Sulthan Sabeel Khan (USN No. 2SU19PM032) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

[Signature]
27/06/2022
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कॉर्पोरेट रिलेशंस एवं कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणंबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST
 भारत सरकार (परतन, पीन परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
 Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
 कार्यालय: पणम्बूर Panambur / मंगलूर, मंगलूर Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Aswin A S (USN No. 2SU19PM011)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
23/06/2022

Dy Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप महाप्रबन्धक-संचार और संपर्क
 Dy Manager (Corp. Relations & Communications)
 नव मंगलूर पोर्ट त्र्यास
 New Mangalore Port Trust
 मंगलूर, मंगलूर - 575010
 Mangalore - 575010

दूरभाष संख्या 0824-2407341
 फ़ैक्स 0824-2408390

दूरभाष-कार्यालय 0824 2407341
 फ़ैक्स 0824 2408390

Phone Office 2407341 (16 Lines)
 Fax 0824 -2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसएसओ 15900:2015
 An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಣಜುರ ಪಂಚಾಯ್ತು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Aromal Sidhardh (USN No. 2SU19PM008) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप नि. प्र. - कार्पोरेट संबंध एवं
Dy Manager - Corp. Relations & Communication
नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणजु, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824-2407341
फैक्स : 0824-2408390

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फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

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आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಣಂಬೂರು ಪಣಬ್ಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರು Mangalore - 575010

SAGARMALA
PORT-LED PROSPERITY

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Akash K Biju (USN No. 2SU19PM006)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Handwritten Signature)
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक - कार्यालय संबंधित प्रशासनिक
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फ़ैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lin
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

CERTIFICATE

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ (ಪತ್ತನ, ಪೊಟ ಪರಿವಹನ ಓರ ಜಲಮಾರ್ಗಿ ಮಂತ್ರಾಲಯ)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪನಾಬುರು ಪನಾಬುರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Aniketh V (USN No. 2SU19PM007) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Aniketh V
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಉಪ ಪ್ರಬಂಧಕ - ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಟ್ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪರ್ಕ
Dy Manager-Corporate Relations & Communication

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪನಾಬುರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ : 0824 - 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

ಆರ್ಟಿಫಿಸಿಯಲ್ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 ಉರ್ದು ಅಂತರರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಅನುಪಾಲನಕರ್ತೃ ಪತ್ತನ
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

COMPANY CERTIFICATE

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಶಿಬಿರವು: ಪಣಬುರ Panambur / ಕಛೇರಿ: ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Muhammed Siraj K K (USN No. 2SU19PM025) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Kandire
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट सम्बन्ध और संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust

पणबुर, मंगलूर - 575010

Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341

ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341

फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)

Fax : 0824 - 2408390

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पोतन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಶಿಬಿರಾಲಯ ಪನ್ಚಮ್ಬರ Panambur / ಕಛೇರಿ: ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Aswin A S (USN No. 2SU19PM011)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Aswin A S
23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ನ್ಯೂ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)
ಶಿಬಿರಾಲಯ ಪನ್ಚಮ್ಬರ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಶಿಬಿರಾಲಯ ಪನ್ಚಮ್ಬರ - 575010
Mangalore - 575010

ಫೋನ್: 0824-2407341
0824-2408390

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ ಕಛೇರಿ: 0824 - 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್: 0824 2408390

Phone Office 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax 0824 -2408390

ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 ಮತ್ತು ISO 45001:2018 ಅನ್ವಯದಲ್ಲಿ
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಟ್ಟಣದ ಪಂಚಾಯ್ತು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 24.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Muhammed Shahin M M** (USN No. 2SU19PM024) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working
We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

for

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट सम्पर्क
Dy Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications
नव मंगलूर पतन त्रास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575 010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575 010

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824-2407341
फैक्स : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 -2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಾನ್‌ಬುರು ಪಂಚಾಯ್ತು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Jai Kumar Singh (USN No. 2SU19PM016) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट, मंगलूर
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communication

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पानंबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lir)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ 9001:2015, 14001:2015 एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
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ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಾಣಜೂರು ಪಣಜೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 27.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Sulthan Sabeel Khan** (USN No. 2SU19PM032) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

[Signature]
27/06/2022
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक - कार्पोरेट रिलेशंस & कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager - Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणजूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ಡ್ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಂಚುರು ಪಣಬುರ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 24.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Muhammed Shahin M M (USN No. 2SU19PM024) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working
We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

for

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक - कॉर्पोरेट संबंध
Dy. Manager, Corporate Relations & Communications
नव मंगलूर पत्तन त्रास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575 010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824-2407341
फैक्स : 0824-2408390

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An ISO 9001:2015, 14001:2015 & ISPS Compliant Port

COMPANY CERTIFICATE (SCANNED CERTIFICATE)

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಫಣಬುರು ಪಣಬುರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Dheeraj (USN No. 2SU19PM015) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक - कॉर्पोरेट रिलेशंस & कम्युनिकेशन

Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

New Mangalore Port Trust

पणबुर्, मंगलूर - 575010

Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

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ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಾನ್‌ಮೂರು ಪಣಮ್ಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. K Benjamin John Simon** (USN No. 2SU19PM018) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

K Benjamin John Simon
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक - कॉर्पोरेट रिलेशंस & कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणमू, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore 575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

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ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ (ಪತ್ತನ, ಪೊನ ಪರಿವಹನ ಔರ ಜಲಮಾರ್ಗ ಮಂತ್ರಾಲಯ)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಂಚೂರು: ಪಣಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂತ್ರೂರು: ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Aswin Pradeep I V** (USN No. 2SU19PM012) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Handwritten signature
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಉಪ ಪ್ರಬಂಧಕ-ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಟ್ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪರ್ಕ
Dy Manager-Corporate Relations & Communication
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪಣಬೂರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur Mangalore - 575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ 0824 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ 0824 2408390

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ 0824 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

Phone Office 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax 0824 - 2408390

ಆರ್ಟಿಎಸ್ಐ 9001 2015, 14001 2015 ಏವ್ ಆರ್ಟಿಎಸ್ಐಎಸ್ ಅನುಪಾಲನ ಕರ್ತೃ ಪತ್ತನ
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ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
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भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ: ಪಂಚಬುರ Panambur / ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ: ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Abdul Azeez V S (USN No. 2SU19PM002) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

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Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications
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New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
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Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಣಬೂರು ಪಣಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Abinsha Nadir (USN No. 2SU19PM003)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

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पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
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No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Adarsh U (USN No. 2SU19PM004) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

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23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

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Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

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Panambur, Mangalore-575010

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फैक्स : 0824-2408390

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No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Mohammed Thoufeeq V B (USN No. 2SU19PM021) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

22/06/2022
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

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Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications
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Panambur, Mangalore-575010

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ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
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ಒಳನಾಡು: ಪಣಬುರ್ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Shebin K (USN No. 2SU19PM030) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

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22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट र्‌लेशंस एंव कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager Corporate Relations & Communications

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New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबुूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

दूरभाष : ०८२४-२४०७३४१
फैक्स : ०८२४-२४०८३९०

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : ०८२४ - २४०७३४१
फैक्स : ०८२४ - २४०८३९०

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

आईएसओ ९००१:२०१५, १४००१:२०१५ एवं आईएसपीएस अनुपालनकर्ता पत्तन
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ಪಾನ್‌ಬುರು ಪಂಚಾಯ್ತು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Dhanush K (USN No. 2SU19PM014) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working. We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

23/06/2022
Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಉಪ ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕ - ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಟ್ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪರ್ಕ
Dy. Manager - Corp. Relations & Communications
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪಾನ್‌ಬುರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ : 0824 - 2407341
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COMPANY CERTIFICATE

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No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 20.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Shibin K S (USN No. 2SU19PM031) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Handwritten Signature)
20/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-व्यापारिक सम्पर्क एवं संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

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New Mangalore Port Trust

पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010

Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : 0824-2407341
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ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ (ಪತ್ತನ, ಛೊನ ಪರಿವಹನ ಔರ ಜಲಮಾರ್ಗ ಮಂತ್ರಾಲಯ)

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ಪಾಣಂಬೂರು ಪಣಮ್ಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 20.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Sanof K R (USN No. 2SU19PM029)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce)** Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.
We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Handwritten signature
20/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಉಪ ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕರು (ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಷನ್ ರಿಲೇಷನ್ಸ್ ಔರ ಕಮ್ಯುನಿಕೇಷನ್)
Dy. Manager (Corporate Relations & Communications)
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪತ್ತನ ನ್ಯಾಸ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪಾಣಂಬೂರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

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ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

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Date: 23.06.2022

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Sandeep S Pillai (USN No. 2SU19PM028) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working. We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

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Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications
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Panambur, Mangalore-575010

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No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Asjoe Shajan (USN No. 2SU19PM010)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ನ್ಯೂ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
Dy Manager, Corporate Relations & Communications
ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
New Mangalore Port Authority
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಚೇರಿ 0824-2407341
ತಾ. ಕಛೇರಿ 0824-2408390

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ಪಂಚೂರು ಪಣಬ್ಬುರ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರ Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Mishal A M (USN No. 2SU19PM020)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.**

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट संपर्क एवं संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

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COMPANY CERTIFICATE

ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास

NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಶಿಖರಾಬು ಪಂಚುರ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಲೂರು - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 24.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Vishnu Vinod (USN No. 2SU19PM034)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.
We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कार्पोरेट संबंध एवं संचार
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पंಚುರ, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಛೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
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Fax : 0824 -2408390

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

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ಪಂಚುಬುರು ಪಂಚುಬುರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangalore - 575010

SAGARMALA
PORT LET PROSPERITY

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Majesh M (USN No. 2SU19PM019)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप-प्रबन्धक (संस्थासंबंधी आणि संचार)
Dy. Manager (Corporate Relations & Communications)

नव मंगलूर पोत मंडळ
New Mangalore Port Trust
पंಚುಬುರು, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

ದೂರವಾರ್ತೆ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

Phone : Office : 2407341 (18 Lines)
Fax : 0824 - 2408390

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)

ಪಣಂಬೂರು ಪಣಂಬೂರು Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಂಗಳೂರು Mangaluru - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 27.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Sulthan Sabeel Khan (USN No. 2SU19PM032) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

Sulthan Sabeel Khan
27/06/2022

John Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक-कॉर्पोरेट रिलेशंस एवं कम्युनिकेशंस
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पत्तन न्यास
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणंबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangaluru - 575010

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : ಕಚೇರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

दूरभाष : कार्यालय : 0824 - 2407341
फैक्स : 0824 - 2408390

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 नव मंगलूर पत्तन त्वास
NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST
 भारत सरकार (परतन, पीन परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
 Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
 कार्यालय: पणम्बूर Panambur / मंगलूर, मंगलूर Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Aswin A S (USN No. 2SU19PM011)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Signature)
23/06/2022

Dy Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप-प्रबंधक-संचार और संपर्क सम्बन्धी कार्य
 Dy Manager (Corp. Relations & Communications)
 नव मंगलूर पोर्ट ट्रस्ट
 New Mangalore Port Trust
 मंगलूर, मंगलूर - 575010
 Mangalore, Mangalore-575010

दूरभाष संख्या 0824-2407341
 फ़ैक्स 0824-2408390

दूरभाष-कार्यालय 0824 2407341
 फ़ैक्स 0824 2408390

Phone Office 2407341 (16 Lines)
 Fax 0824 -2408390

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ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಬಂದರು ಮಂಡಳಿ
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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)
Govt of India (Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways)
ಪಣಜುರ Panambur / ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಮಗಲೂರು Mangalore - 575010

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 23.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Aromal Sidhardh (USN No. 2SU19PM008) student of BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru has successfully completed his Internship at New Mangalore Port Authority from 05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

23/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

ಡಿ. ಮ್ಯಾನೇಜರ್ - ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಟ್ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪರ್ಕ
Dy. Manager - Corp. Relations & Communication
ನವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಪಟ್ಟಣ ನ್ಯಾಸ
New Mangalore Port Trust
ಪಣಜುರ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore - 575010

ಫೋನ್ : ಕಛೆರಿ : 0824-2407341
ಫೋನ್ : 0824-2408390

ಫೋನ್ : ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ : 0824 - 2407341
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824 - 2408390

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NEW MANGALORE PORT TRUST

भारत सरकार (पत्तन, पोत परिवहन और जलमार्ग मंत्रालय)

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SAGARMALA
PORT-LED PROSPERITY

No.5/1/TRG/Intern/2022-23

Date: 22.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Akash K Biju (USN No. 2SU19PM006)** student of **BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Commerce) Srinivas University, Mangaluru** has successfully completed his Internship at **New Mangalore Port Authority** from **05.01.2022 to 05.04.2022**.

During this training period, we found him sincere and hard working.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavor.

(Handwritten Signature)
22/06/2022

Dy. Manager (Corp. Relations & Comm.)

उप प्रबंधक - कार्यालय संबंधित प्रशासनिक
Dy. Manager-Corporate Relations & Communications

नव मंगलूर पोत मंडळ
New Mangalore Port Trust
पणंबूर, मंगलूर - 575010
Panambur, Mangalore-575010

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ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2408390

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फक्स : 0824 - 2408390

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